

Investigation of Water Quality in Aizawl City, Mizoram, India

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Abstract:

Water derived from various sources may differ greatly in quality and suitability for domestic use. Ideally, water intended for human consumption must be free from organisms and from concentration of chemical substances that may be hazardous to health. In addition, supplies of drinking water should be as pleasant to drink as circumstances permit. Coolness, absence of turbidity and colour and absence of any disagreeable taste or smell are of the utmost importance in public supplies of drinking water. Drinking water or

potable water is water of sufficiently high quality that it can be consumed or used without risk of immediate or long-term harm to human health. Water samples from different water sources were collected for testing the quality. Fifteen samples each from tuikhur and hand pumps, one sample each from River Tlawng and Serlui, one sample each from three springs located outside the residential area from where water tankers collect water, five samples of rainwater, and five samples from piped water supply. All together forty-five water samples were collected and tested for physical, chemical and bacteriological parameters.

Keywords: *Physical, Chemical, Bacteriological, Parameters.*

Introduction

The term quality as applied to water embraces the combined physical, chemical, radiological and biological characteristics of the most abundant compound on the surface of the earth. Water is vital to the existence of all life forms, as we know it and is essential either directly or indirectly to almost all activities of human beings. Water quality is a dominant factor in determining the adequacy of any supply to satisfy the requirements of the different uses and users. Water quality is determined by analytically measuring the concentrations of the various constituents and the effects or properties caused by the presence of these substances. In determining the quality of a natural water-supply source, the procedures used in sampling the supply are very important. The units of

expression of water quality are significant too, since there are possibilities of confusion and misinterpretation of water-quality data.

The quality of water that is consumed is well-recognised as an important transmission route for infectious diarrhoeal and other diseases (WHO, 1993). The importance of water quality continues to be emphasised by its role in epidemics and contribution to endemic disease from pathogens (Ford, 1999; Payment and Hunter, 2001). This affects both developed and developing countries, although the majority of the health burden is carried by children in developing countries (Prüss *et al.*, 2002; WHO, 2000). However, recent outbreaks such as that of cryptosporidiosis in Milwaukee and *E.coli* O157:H7 and *Campylobacter jejuni* in Walkerton, Ontario illustrate that the developed world also

remains at risk (Mackenzie *et al.*, 1994; O'Connor, 2002).

The WHO Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality assess the health risks posed by contaminants in drinking water. In most developing countries, including India, the primary contaminant of surface and ground water is human and animal waste. The WHO guidelines suggest that *E. coli* (the indicator organism for bacterial contamination) should not be detectable in a 100-ml sample of water, but with fewer than 10 coliforms, the water is considered to be of 'moderately' good quality (WHO, 1993, 1997, 2008).

Water provided for direct consumption and ingestion via food should be of a quality that does not represent a significant risk to human health. A zero-risk scenario for public supplies is not achievable and evidence points to the need to define tolerable risks, commonly based on estimates of numbers of excess cases per defined population size. This approach underpins much risk assessment thinking within the water sector for both microbial and chemical contaminants (Fewtrell and Bartram, 2001; Haas *et al.*, 1999; WHO, 1996).

The adverse impacts on public health from poor water supply have long been recognised in both developing and developed countries and take the form of outbreaks and contribution to background rates of disease (Esrey *et al.*, 1991; Ford, 1999; Payment and Hunter, 2001). Nevertheless, reliable estimates of the global burden of disease related to water, sanitation and hygiene are only now becoming available (Prüss *et al.*, 2002). Waterborne disease contributes a significant proportion of the total disease burden associated with diarrhoea and other gastrointestinal diseases (WHO, 2002).

Almost 80 per cent of all diseases in the world are related to health damaging water and poor sanitation (UN, 2003). In many cases, the use of piped water may seem to lead to improved health (Tumwine, 2002; Shi, 2000). In developing countries, of the 37 diseases identified as major causes of death, 21 are related to water and sanitation. The issue of quantity and quality of water thus becomes a fundamental basis of life

(APPEN, 1998). In China, widespread access to safe drinking water and sanitation has minimised the adverse impacts on health despite high levels of pollution of water sources (World Bank, 1997).

Study Area

Aizawl, the capital of Mizoram state, is situated in on the hillcrests, steep slopes and small valleys. It is located on a north-south elongated ridge, which acts as the main hill from which many small ridges and valleys are extending towards the east and west directions. The topography is highly undulating and rugged. The unique physical attributes of this rugged land are marked by extreme fragility and frequent landslides, limited land space, steep slopes and lack of accessibility. The city reveals a rapid and uncontrolled growth pattern with multi-storey settlements that has mushroomed unplanned on highly risk prone slopes. The altitude varies from 120 m to 1400 m above mean sea level. It falls between 23° 40' N to 23° 50' N latitudes and 92° 40' E to 92° 49' E longitudes. It covers an area of about 128.98 sq km, and as per Aizawl Municipal Corporation Report 2020, the population is 3,59,829 persons.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are as follows:

- 1) to investigate the quality of water from various domestic water sources in Aizawl city, and
- 2) to compare the quality of these water with standard drinking water quality

Data Base and Methodology

Water samples from different water sources were collected for testing the quality. Fifteen samples each from *tuikbur* and hand pumps, one sample each from River *Tlawng* and *Serlui*, one sample each from three springs located outside the residential area from where water tankers collect water, five samples of rainwater, and five samples from piped water supply. All together forty-five water samples were collected and tested for physical, chemical and bacteriological

parameters. Water Samples have been collected at morning, except samples collected from rainwater and piped water. One litre of water was taken for each sample. Bottle in which samples are collected was clean, sterilised plastic bottle, narrow mouthed neutral plastic stopper. The bottles are washed by detergent and dry by air. The samples water was immediately brought to the PHED, laboratory at *Tuikbuahtlang* for analysis. Analysis has been done in the laboratory by department technicians.

The physical quality of samples water testing was carried out by using the parameters of odour, taste, colour and turbidity. The chemical quality was tested by looking the properties of pH, alkalinity, chloride, hardness, iron, fluoride and total dissolve solids. Bacteriological testing was performed by counting total coliform bacteria. The result of sample water test has been compared with the International Standard of Drinking Water Quality prepared by WHO (2008). This process helped to examine the technical safety of water from the sample sources.

Results and Discussion

Water for domestic use is required to be both wholesome and safe. For aesthetic reasons it is desirable that the water be clear (low turbidity) and that it be free from taste, odour and colour. For health reason, a number of chemical characteristics need to be considered. The basic requirements for drinking water are that it should be free from pathogenic (disease causing) organisms; clear (low turbidity), not saline (salty); free from offensive taste or smell; free from compounds that may have adverse effects on human health (harmful in the short or long term); and free from chemicals that may cause corrosion or encrustation. Water quality parameters are divided into four main aspects: physical, chemical, radiological and bacteriological (WHO, 2008). The quality of water from different sources in Aizawl has been analysed accordingly in the following lines except for radiological parameter.

Physical Parameters

The physical characteristics of sampled water collected from different sources of water in Aizawl City are summarised in Table 1 to 5.

Colour: Levels of colour below 15 TCU are usually acceptable to consumers, but acceptability may vary. High colour could also indicate a high propensity to produce by-products from disinfection processes. No health based guideline value is proposed for colour in drinking water (WHO, 2008). All water samples are colourless except samples of ground water collected from *Electric Veng* and *Chawnpui*, which are detected as yellowish red and brownish colour, respectively.

Taste and Odour: Taste and odour, though of great importance in assessing the palatability of water are the most difficult physical characteristics to measure in any numerical sense. Objection to taste and odour in drinking water is very subjective in nature and different persons react differently to them. The present analysis shows that all water samples are found as tasteless and odourless.

Turbidity: No health based guideline value for turbidity has been proposed (WHO, 2008). The turbidity value of the water from *tuikbur* has been found in the range of less than 1.0 NTU to 1.0 NTU, whereas the ground water was in the range of less than 1.0 NTU to greater than 5 NTU. The ground water having turbidity value of greater than 5 NTU was found in *Chawnpui*. Piped water and rainwater have a turbidity value of less than 1.0 NTU. It is very interesting to note that the turbidity value of River *Tlawng* and its tributary *Serlui* is 10 NTU and 5 NTU, respectively. It reveals that the raw water of River *Tlawng* and *Serlui* might be unfit for drinking purpose without treatment as far as the turbidity is concerned. Spring located along *Tlawng* road have a turbidity value of 2 NTU, while the other two springs located at *Tuirial* road have the value of 1 NTU and less than 1.0 NTU.

Table 1. Physical Quality Water of Tuikhur in Aizawl

Name of Local Council	Odour	Taste	Colour	Turbidity
Mission Veng	odourless	tasteless	colourless	1.0 NTU
Bethlehem Veng	odourless	tasteless	colourless	1.0 NTU
Ramthar	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Kulikawn	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Electric Veng	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Chaltlang	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Bungkawn	odourless	tasteless	colourless	1.0 NTU
Chanmari 'W'	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Republic Veng	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Khatla	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Chhinga Veng	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Tuikual 'S'	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Venghlui	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Ramhlun 'S'	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Chawlhmun	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU

Table 2. Physical Quality of Ground Water in Aizawl

Name of Local Council	Odour	Taste	Colour	Turbidity
Ramthar	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Bungkawn	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Luangmual	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Ramhlun 'S'	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Kulikawn	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Mission Veng	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Zemabawk	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Republic Veng	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Khatla	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Chhinga Veng	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Electric Veng	odourless	Tasteless	Yellowish Red	> 1.0 NTU
Zonuam	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Chawnpui	odourless	Tasteless	Brownish	< 5 NTU
Bawngkawn	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Durtlang	odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU

Table 3. Physical Quality of Piped Water in Aizawl

Name of Sources	Odour	Taste	Colour	Turbidity
H. Connection	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Zonal Tank	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
M. Reservoir	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Zonal Tank	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Reservoir	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU

Table 4. Physical Quality of Rainwater in Aizawl

Name of Sources	Odour	Taste	Colour	Turbidity
Roof	Odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Tank	Odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Cistern	Odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Roof	Odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU
Tank	Odourless	Tasteless	Colourless	> 1.0 NTU

Table 5. Physical Quality Water of Rivers and Springs in and Around Aizawl

Name of Source	Odour	Taste	Colour	Turbidity
River (<i>Tlawng</i>)	odourless	tasteless	colourless	10.0 NTU
River (<i>Serlui</i>)	odourless	tasteless	colourless	5.0 NTU
Spring (<i>Tlawng</i> road)	odourless	tasteless	colourless	2.0 NTU
Spring (<i>Tuirial</i> road)	odourless	tasteless	colourless	1.0 NTU
Spring (<i>Tuirial</i> road)	odourless	tasteless	colourless	> 1.0 NTU

Chemical Parameters

The chemical characteristics of drinking water in the study area are examined by using seven parameters, such as pH, alkalinity, chloride, hardness, iron, fluoride and total dissolved solids. Other chemical contaminants identified as potential health problems, such as nitrate, sulphate, arsenic, cadmium, etc. are not found in the water of the study area. The chemical characteristics of water samples collected from different sources are shown in Table 6 to 10.

pH: Although pH usually has no direct impact on consumers, it is one of the most important operational water quality parameters and the optimum pH required often being in the range 6.5 to 9.5 (WHO, 2008). The pH value of water of *tuikbur* ranges from 6.1 to 7.0 (average 6.8), of ground water between 6.6 and 7.2 (average 6.8), of piped water from 6.9 to 7.1 (average 7), and of rainwater between 6.5 and 6.9 (average 6.7). The pH of River *Tlawng* is 6.8, while of *Serlui* is 7. Springs water has pH from 6.6 to 7. Therefore, the pH of one *tuikbur* located in *Electric Veng* is lower than the permissible limit for drinking purpose, and the rest are within the range of permissible limit. On an average, piped water has the highest pH value, while rainwater has the least value. In general, water is slightly acidic in nature.

Alkalinity: Alkalinity is a measure of the acid-neutralizing capacity of water. The aesthetic objective is set at a maximum of 500 ppm (WHO, 2008). The alkalinity concentration in water of *tuikbur* varies from 16 ppm to 100 ppm, in ground water ranges from 30 ppm to 170 ppm, in piped water from 68 ppm to 120 ppm, and in rainwater from 20 ppm to 70 ppm. The alkalinity concentration in River *Tlawng* is 38 ppm, and 58 ppm in River *Ser*. The alkalinity value in springs located at *Tlawng* road, and

Tuirial road ranges from 46 ppm to 94 ppm. Taking into average, piped water has the highest concentration of alkalinity (89.2 ppm), whereas rainwater (30 ppm) has the lowest concentration. Despite the alkalinity concentration varies widely all water samples are within the permissive limit.

Chloride: No health based guideline value for chloride in drinking water was proposed in the 2008 Guidelines, although it was confirmed that chloride concentrations in excess of about 250 mg/litre could give rise to detectable taste in water (WHO, 2008). The primary objection of the presence of chloride in the excessive quantity in domestic water supply is due to the salty taste that imparts to the water. In brief, all water samples chloride content is within the safe limit for drinking purpose that is below 250 ppm.

Hardness: The first edition of WHO Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality, published in 1984, concluded that there was no firm evidence that drinking hard water causes any adverse effects on human health and that no recommendation on the restriction of municipal water softening or on the maintenance of a minimum residual calcium or magnesium level was warranted. A guideline value of 500 mg/litre (as calcium carbonate) was established for hardness, based on taste and household use considerations (WHO, 2008).

The present analysis reveals that the total hardness of water of *tuikbur* range from 50 ppm to 220 ppm, ground water from 60 ppm to 232 ppm, piped water from 62 ppm to 80 ppm, and rainwater from 18 ppm to 80 ppm. Springs' water hardness ranges from 54 ppm to 120 ppm. The total hardness of River *Tlawng* and *Serlui* is 42 ppm and 60 ppm, respectively. Interestingly, in all water samples values of hardness were found to be well within the desirable limits specifications for drinking water quality. The

lower values of hardness may be attributed to the effect of rainfall that tends to decrease the values of bicarbonates and ultimately the hardness. Total hardness is essential from potability point of view as there is a danger of heavy metals dissolving easily in soft water with low pH, and making it toxic.

Iron: The WHO (1958), Standards for Drinking water suggested that concentrations of iron greater than 1.0 mg/litre would markedly impair the potability of the water. No health based guideline value for iron in drinking water was proposed in the 2008 Guidelines (WHO, 2008). Two water samples from *tuikhur* located in *Chaltlang* and *Chawlhbmun* local councils and eight ground water samples are beyond the permissive limit in the study area.

Fluoride: The 2008 Guidelines concluded that there was no evidence to suggest that the guideline value of 1.5 mg/litre set in 1984 needed to be revised (WHO, 2008). Fluoride is traced in eight water samples from *tuikhur* and nine samples of ground water, two samples of rainwater and all piped water samples. However,

the values of fluoride in these samples are quite significantly lower than the upper limits.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS): The presence of high levels of TDS in drinking water (greater than 1000 mg/litre) may be objectionable to consumers. Water with extremely low concentrations of TDS may also be unacceptable because of its flat, insipid taste (WHO, 2008). Dissolved solids represent the approximate total quantity of dissolved mineral constituents in the water. Based on the WHO (2008) guidelines, water with less than 600 ppm of dissolved solids is considered satisfactory for domestic uses. The dissolved solid content of water samples of *tuikhur* range from 126 ppm to 418 ppm, ground water from 192 ppm to 512 ppm, piped water from 168 ppm to 252 ppm, and rainwater from 48 ppm to 156 ppm. Dissolved solids of 120 ppm and 168 ppm were observed in River *Tlawng* and *Serlui*, respectively. No samples are found beyond permissive limit. On an average, the dissolved solid content is high in ground water, while it is low in rainwater.

Table 6. Physical Quality of Water of Tuikhur in Aizawl (in ppm)

Name of Local Council	pH	Alkalinity	Chloride	Hardness	Iron	Fluoride	TDS
Mission Veng	6.7	72	80	106	Nil	Nil	310
Bethlehem Veng	6.8	42	40	106	Trace	Nil	226
Ramthar	6.8	16	95	220	Trace	Nil	397
Kulikawn	7	50	120	156	Trace	Nil	391
Electric Veng	6.1	20	115	210	Trace	Nil	414
Chaltlang	7	98	70	180	0.5	Nil	418
Bungkawn	6.6	24	50	94	Trace	Nil	202
Chanmari 'W'	6.8	38	20	106	Trace	Trace	197
Republic Veng	6.8	100	70	160	0.1	Trace	396
Khatla	6.8	40	50	80	Trace	Trace	204
Chhinga Veng	6.8	36	61	106	Trace	Trace	244
Tuikual 'S'	6.8	32	45	50	Trace	Trace	152
Venghlui	6.8	40	70	100	Trace	Trace	252
Ramhlun 'S'	7	38	60	100	Trace	Trace	238
Chawlhbmun	7	80	30	60	1.4	Trace	204
Average	6.8	48.4	65.06	122.26	0.66	Trace	283

Table 7. Chemical Quality of Ground Water in Aizawl (in ppm)

Name of Local Council	pH	Alkalinity	Chloride	Hardness	Iron	Fluoride	TDS
Ramthar	7	130	38	200	0.2	Nil	442
Nursery Veng	6.6	100	16	100	0.4	Nil	259

Luangmual	6.8	170	25	232	3.6	Nil	512
Ramhlun 'S'	6.8	80	30	96	1	Nil	247
Kulikawn	6.8	80	45	120	Trace	Trace	294
Mission Veng	7.2	80	89	98	Trace	Nil	320
Zemabawk	6.8	70	68	150	0.1	Nil	346
Republic Veng	6.8	50	55	120	2	Trace	270
Khatla	6.8	44	50	70	Trace	Trace	197
Chhinga Veng	6.8	32	50	116	0.1	0.1	238
Electric Veng	6.7	52	70	100	0.5	0.1	266
Zonuam	6.9	60	45	60	0.5	Trace	198
Chawnpui	6.8	150	15	200	2	Trace	438
Bawngkawn	7	30	30	100	0.2	0.1	192
Durtlang	7	80	20	60	1	Trace	192
Average	6.85	80.53	43.06	121.46	0.96	0	294.06

Table 8. Chemical Quality of Piped Water in Aizawl (in ppm)

Name of Source	pH	Alkalinity	Chloride	Hardness	Iron	Fluoride	TDS
H. Connection	6.9	80	5	70	Trace	Trace	186
Zonal Tank	7	120	10	80	Trace	Trace	252
M. Reservoir	7.1	80	5	62	Trace	Trace	176
Zonal Tank	7	68	10	62	Trace	Trace	168
Reservoir	7	98	5	80	Trace	Trace	220
Average	7	89.2	7	70.8	Trace	Trace	200.4

Table 9. Chemical Quality of Rainwater in Aizawl (in ppm)

Name of Source	pH	Alkalinity	Chloride	Hardness	Iron	Fluoride	TDS
Roof	6.5	20	25	80	Trace	Nil	150
Tank	6.6	20	15	18	0.1	Nil	64
Cistern	6.8	20	NIL	20	Trace	Trace	48
Roof	6.9	70	Trace	60	NIL	NIL	156
Tank	6.8	20	NIL	20	Trace	Trace	48
Average	6.72	30	20	39.6	Trace	0	93.2

Table 10. Chemical Quality of Water of Rivers and Springs in and Around Aizawl (in ppm)

Name of Source	pH	Alkalinity	Chloride	Hardness	Iron	Fluoride	TDS
River (<i>Tlawng</i>)	6.8	38	20	42	Trace	Nil	120
River (<i>Tlawng</i>)	6.8	38	20	42	Trace	Nil	120
River (<i>Serlui</i>)	7	58	22	60	Trace	Nil	168
Spring (<i>Tlawng</i> road)	6.8	56	20	68	Trace	Nil	173
Spring (<i>Tuirial</i> road)	6.6	46	5	54	Trace	Nil	126
Spring (<i>Tuirial</i> road)	7	94	9	120	0.2	Nil	268
Average	6.84	58.4	15.2	68.8	Trace	0	171

Based on the physio-chemical characteristics studies of water in the study area for drinking purpose it can be stated that piped water, rainwater and water of springs located outside the residential area are adequately safe and do not pose any serious threat to the human health.

Simultaneously, water of two *tuikbur* from *Chaltlang* and *Chawlbhmun* local councils may be objectionable without treatment for drinking purpose due to excess content of iron. In addition, of the total ground water samples, eight samples contained excess iron and may also be

objectionable. It seems that due to high concentration of iron in ground water, people reject hand pumps during the normal period. Certainly, high concentration of iron in water affects the taste and smell of the water. The turbidity value of River *Tlawng* is also unacceptable for drinking purpose without being treated; meanwhile the other physio-chemical characteristics are of good quality.

Bacteriological Parameter

Drinking water quality objectives do not stop with merely making available water in adequate quantity and of satisfactory physical and chemical quality. If the water is to be safe it should necessarily be bacteriologically pure so as to avoid any public health hazards. Microbiological quality is by many authors claimed to be a key concern for promotion of good health (Drangert, 1993; Howard, 2002). Maximum acceptable concentration for drinking water has been set at no organism detectable/100 ml (WHO, 2008).

The bacteriological testing reveals that piped water and rainwater are of very good microbiological quality and have no counts of coliform bacteria. Table 11 presents the bacteriological testing result of water samples collected from *tuikbur*. Of the total water samples from *tuikbur*, seven samples have counts of coliform bacteria, i.e., 46.66 per cent of the total samples collected from *tuikbur*. The number of coliform counts varies widely and it ranges from 22 to 70 coliforms in 100 ml water sample. Of the total ground water samples, six samples, i.e., 40 per cent have counts of coliform (Table 12). The number of coliform counts in ground water samples range from 22 to 180 coliforms. Sample water collected from River *Tlawng* and *Serlui* have counts of 1,790 and 3500 coliforms bacteria, respectively. Springs located at River *Tlawng* road and River *Tuirial* road where private tankers collect water were also found with substantial amount of coliform (Table 13).

Therefore, the bacteriological analysis reveals that 46.66 per cent of water samples of *tuikbur* and 40 per cent of ground water samples are contaminated, hence not suitable for direct consumption without proper treatment. The

lack of a sewage system has contributed to a phenomenon called flying buckets - people defecate in polythene bags, which they then throw in to drainage channels or wherever they find it convenient. The sum is a very unhygienic environment, with obvious danger to water sources. A blocked drainage channel can lead to stagnant water, resulting in contamination of ground water. It may also result in favourable breeding conditions for mosquitoes capable of transmitting diseases like malaria. *Tuikbur* are usually found at breaks of slope between the hillsides and wetlands, where the ground water table is close to the surface. As is the case of *tuikbur* and hand pumps in the study area, there are often dwellings with septic tank soak pit on the upward slopes. These must be regarded as the major source of contamination of water sources. In fact, the number of coliforms count is a substantial amount, considering that the national standard for drinking water quality is zero/100ml. Also WHO (1993) states that there should be no bacteria indicating faecal pollution in water intended for human consumption. River *Tlawng* and *Serlui* and springs located at *Tlawng* road and *Tuirial* road are also contaminated, commercial water tankers used to collect water from these points and supply to the residents without treatment, the fate of the people can just imagined in the study area.

Table 11. Bacteriological Testing of Water of *Tuikbur* in Aizawl

Name of Local Council	Coliform Counts (per 100 ml of water)
Mission Veng	0
Bethlehem Veng	22
Ramthar	40
Kulikawn	0
Electric Veng	37
Chaltlang	0
Bungkawn	0
Chanmari 'W'	46
Republic Veng	70
Khatla	0
Chhinga Veng	42
Tuikual 'S'	58
Venghlui	0
Ramhlun 'S'	0
Chawlhmun	0

Table 12. Bacteriological Testing of Ground Water in Aizawl

Name of Local Council	Coliform Counts (per 100 ml of sample water)
Ramthar	22
Nursery Veng	0
Luangmual	0
Ramhlun 'S'	120
Kulikawn	0
Mission Veng	180
Zemabawk	0
Republic Veng	92
Khatla	0
Chhinga Veng	78
Electric Veng	65
Zonuam	0
Chawnpui	0
Bawngkawn	0
Durtlang	0

Table 13. Bacteriological Testing of Water of Rivers and Springs in and Around Aizawl

Name of Source	Coliform Counts (per 100 ml of sample water)
River (<i>Tlawng</i>)	1790
River (<i>Serlui</i>)	3500
Spring (<i>Tlawng</i> road)	20
Spring (<i>Tuirial</i> road)	15
Spring (<i>Tuirial</i> road)	130

Lack of focus on the microbiological quality of water covers both lack of willingness/ability to focus and lack of awareness. An awareness of the microbiological content does not imply people being able to explain the details of disease transmission. It only implies recognition of that there are health dangers connected to use of water with a high content of bacteria. On being asked about their perception about attributes of safe drinking water, almost all the respondents have mentioned that what looks clean is clean and safe. Tastes good was considered as an attribute of safe. It is obvious that most of the respondents considered visibly clean water as safe water. Usually, water that is clear and colourless gives expression that it is safe for human consumption. However, this may not be true as many of the bacteria and objectionable matter may be present in invisible form.

Interviews with respondents and civil servants dealing with water and health indicate a lack of good communication between them. An example of this is that residents claim that they are not informed about results of water quality tests. There is not a stable and enduring cooperation between the authorities and the residents regarding health aspects. Such failure to inform and create awareness among the public clearly hinders improvements in health safety practices among people. Sporadic and insufficient health information may in worst cases lead to misunderstandings. It is believed that some sort of lack of focus on the microbiological content of water can be related to an understanding of reality emphasizing visible facts. Further, bacteriological tolerance is believed to be a central factor hindering more attention to this issue. However, one must not forget that economical scarcity is a limiting factor on the number of choices. Water from traditional sources may therefore be chosen on this basis.

Increasing efforts on community water education enhances households' awareness about water quality issues. Teaching them to differentiate the 'actual' from the 'perceived' quality of water and helping them to realize the benefits of improved water management can ensure better participation in water source management initiatives. Considering the fact that a good number of water sources have some total coliform bacteria, it is apparent that efforts are necessary to improve the safety of water from the sources. This can be made with source disinfection mechanisms such as chlorination or point-of-use disinfection mechanisms such as boiling to decrease the bacteriological health hazards.

Conclusion

The study of physio-chemical characteristics of water quality in the study area reveals that piped water, rainwater and water of springs located outside the residential area are suitable for drinking purpose. At the same time, 13.33 per cent of water samples of *tuikbur* and 66.66 per cent of ground water samples are found

objectionable for drinking purpose due to excess content of iron. It seems that high concentration of iron in ground water may be the reason for rejection of using hand pumps during the normal period by residents of Aizawl. The bacteriological testing shows that piped water and rainwater are of very good microbiological quality and have no counts of coliform bacteria. Surprisingly, 46.66 per cent of water samples of *tuikbur* and 40 per cent of ground water samples are not fit for human consumption due to the presence of coliform bacteria. As expected, water of River *Tlawng* and *Serlui* has counts of 1,790 and 3500 coliforms bacteria, respectively. Moreover, springs located at *Tlawng* road and *Tuirial* road, from where private tankers collect water, are also not fit for human consumption as far as their coliform bacteria content is concerned.

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